

Semantic Representation Challenges in AAS, ECLASS and SAMM

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AAS

Asset Administration Shell (AAS) is the hottest new standard in Industrial Digital Twins, with a large development community, investments (by the German government, but also companies), and international following. AAS defines multiple payload formats (XML, JSON, RDF) but the majority of implementations use JSON. As can be expected, AAS is a complex data model that represents the structure and hierarchy of digital twins, various product properties through globally defined "semantics", and allows the incorporation ("enveloping") of other payloads (eg OPC UA, AutomationML, DEXPI P&ID). Numerous AAS "submodels" have been defined (over 50) covering a variety of relevant topics.

Multiple sources have confirmed that being able to query AAS using a generic query language like SPARQL has a lot of potential and adds a lot of value. Since AAS API does not include a query endpoint, currently implementers rely on JSON processing and fixed APIs to fetch the required data and perform query operations programmatically on client side.

SPARQL could be promising here to directly expose advanced query capabilities on AAS servers and to use its federated querying on client side. As a prerequisite, a solid RDF-based AAS representation aligned with linked-data principles and web naming conventions (IRIs) is required.

The Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA) Ontologies WG is already working on better integrating AAS and RDF-based knowledge graphs. Within AIOTI we'd like to take this on another level by starting a greater effort to identify possible use cases of an AAS-RDF-integration and to develop a solid base for integrating AAS and knowledge graphs.

The initial RDF serialization for AAS is just a verbatim copy of the XML and JSON formats with multiple problems. The AAS RDF representation has even been dropped in latest versions of major AAS projects.

- Naming conventions for assigning IRIs to AAS elements are not defined. All elements are modeled as blank nodes and hence are not referrable using linked-data principles.
- Property IRIs are prefixed by class name, e.g.
`https://admin-shell.io/aas/3/0/RC01/AssetAdministrationShell/assetInfor`

mation

This is neither aligned with the XML and JSON serialization - that just use plain property names - nor with common practices for RDF vocabulary engineering. Properties should be reusable across multiple classes.

- References may contain multiple hops (via “keys”) and do not align well with direct IRI-based references as used in RDF. A mapping and resolution mechanism needs to be developed that allows navigation of references via SPARQL.
- Semantic IDs are currently represented as string literals. It would be good if these could follow common linked-data practices by being interpretable as IRIs and resolvable on the web.
- Multi-language properties could be simplified by using native RDF mechanisms (rdf:langString)

The IDTA Ontologies WG is already working on some of these challenges to better integrate AAS and RDF-based knowledge graphs.

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Even though IDTA is in progress to introduce a simplified query API, most reference implementations like Eclipse BaSyx or Eclipse FA³ST directly store the JSON representation of AAS in a document DB like MongoDB. The only open-source implementation that uses an RDBMS is the Eclipse AASX server, but it uses a very simple schema.

The structure of AAS includes references, hierarchy and links to other elements, e.g. RelationshipElements, ReferenceElement, etc. So AAS is actually a graph and graph query languages like SPARQL or ISO GQL can be the best choice for querying AAS. The value of SPARQL querying for AAS has been [recognized in the German Factory-X project](#), of which Siemens and Fraunhofer IWU are key developers (through the [LinkedFactory Pod](#) open source project). SPARQL queries offer a lot greater flexibility than REST APIs based on a limited selection of querying options. And since the RDF representation of AAS is fixed, queries are potentially reusable and can use SPARQL Federation to integrate distributed AAS resources.

A number of relevant issues have been raised on Github:

[RDF-native interpretation/profile \(#384\)](#): root RDF issue in the [admin-shell-io/aas-specs](#) project:

- Properties in RDF are prefixed by class names (property IRIs do not follow best practices) [#43](#)
- Ordered keys of references in RDF (Representation is not lossless) [#45](#)
- Plural form of properties in RDF ontology [#163](#)
- Naming scheme for AAS objects (identifiables and references) in RDF [#166](#)
- XSD data types instead of xsd:string for value type (everything is xsd:string) ([#284](#))
- Enable the use of custom datatypes (for RDF) [#380](#)
- Enable the use of lang tags for langString (MultiLanguage properties do not use rdf:langString) [#382](#)
- Linked Data principle and best practices are not utilized [#383](#)
- Official examples do not follow best practices:
 - Wrong namespace for properties in RDF examples [#164](#)
 - Relative URL without base in RDF examples [#379](#)
 - Examples use invalid lang tags [#387](#)
- Improve SHACL schema (SHACL is invalid and has many problems) [#421](#)

ECLASS

ECLASS is a comprehensive product type classification and a data dictionary for describing product properties, and is thus a foundation for interoperable vendor product catalogs. It has the same structure as the IEC 61360 Component Data Dictionary (CDD), based on the "OntoML" 13584-32 standard. It is used widely in AAS to provide shared "semantics" of product properties. The ECLASS association has worked on a semantic representation for 4 years and published the first part of a semantic specification half a year ago: [ECLASS Serialization as RDF, Part 1](#), ECLASS Technical Specification 110, 22 April 2024. This is the first part of a series:

- Part 1: ECLASS Base Model & ECLASS Content
- Part 2: ECLASS Validation with SHACL & SPARQL
- Part 3: ECLASS RDF Usage
 - Part 3.a: RDF product description based on ECLASS
 - Part 3.b: Usage of ECLASS RDF in W3C Web of Things (WoT) Thing Description
 - Part 3.c: Usage of ECLASS RDF in AAS

These parts are still pending, but an older paper can serve as insight into part 3.c: [Modelling the Semantics of Data of an Asset Administration Shell with Elements of ECLASS V. 1.0](#) Date: 2021-06-29.

4 years ago we participated in the ECLASS Semantics WG and made a comprehensive comparison to product representation approaches that are more grounded in real-world objects, eg Schema.org product classes and the GS1 WebVoc. Some of these criticisms are still valid, most importantly:

- ECLASS' modeling methodology (OntoML) doesn't promote "Ontological realism". E.g. instead of product parts and documents, it talks about blocks, aspects, polymorphism, cardinalities.
- ECLASS properties are grouped by blocks and aspects, e.g. Manufacturer Aspect includes attributes like Manufacturer Name and SKU. However, these belong to two different objects: Organization vs ProductModel.
- This also makes it harder to reuse external LOD, e.g. a KG of Companies: in such case Manufacturer Name would also be repeated redundantly at the product level.
- ECLASS class and property URLs are unstable at 2 levels: ECLASS namespace has the base number, and each term uses a versioned IRDI (the last part is a counter)
- ECLASS properties cannot be used in AAS except by copying.

And there are some new problems related to ECLASS semantic representation, as listed in AAS issue ECLASS RDF Representation [#422](#):

- All ECLASS props are ObjectProps, and a lot of them go through a "parasitic" node (ie: `iec61360:IntType`) before they reach the literal `iec61360:value`
- `subPropertyOf` is used as a mere hierarchical organization device rather than with its proper semantics of inferring new triples, eg
 - `<p> rdfs:subPropertyOf eclass:condition: will derive <x> eclass:condition <y> for each <x> <p> <y>`, which is pointless.
Better make a new class `eclass:ConditionalProperty; rdfs:subClassOf ec:ObjectProperty` then `<p> rdf:type eclass:ConditionalProperty.`
 - a whole bunch of `iec61360:value` sub-props like `numerator`, `denominator`, `lePart`, `xValue`, `xRotValue`... What is the purpose of inferring that each of these is also value?

semantic data models and does not include any instance data. ESMF and SAMM use RDF at their core to define models, but semantics is used only as a **means** but not as an end-goal:

- Properties of aspects are explicitly enumerated in **rdf:Lists** enforcing closed-world interpretations by preventing future extension with additional properties.
- Product/machine properties are modeled with classes (saam:Aspect, saam:Property; similar to ECLASS Aspects), rather than straight RDF properties.
- A URN-based strict naming scheme is only compatible with SAMM itself. This prevents semantic resolution, and reuse of external vocabularies and standards (similar to Microsoft Azure DTDL naming schemas). We should open up SAMM models for linking with existing vocabularies.
- OWL and SHACL are widely used in the semantic community to define data schemas. It would be worthy to better align SAMM with those technologies.

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